

Kinetics of Oxidation of Glycerol by Alkaline Potassium Hexacyanoferrate (III) Catalysed by Osmium Tetroxide

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The oxidation kinetics of glycerol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) in presence of Osmium tetroxide as catalyst has been studied. The reaction has been found to have first order dependence in glycerol, sodium hydroxide and the catalyst concentration and independent of the oxidant concentration. The effect of addition of neutral salts like potassium chloride and potassium sulphate is positive. The energy and entropy of activation have been calculated as 12.23 Kcals. and -25.1 e.u. A tentative mechanism has been suggested which is in agreement with the experimental results.

POTASSIUM hexacyanoferrate (III) has been found to be a good oxidizing agent in alkaline medium and the kinetics of oxidation of a number of organic and inorganic compounds with this oxidant has been studied by previous workers¹⁻⁶. The oxidation reactions involving this reagent have been found to be catalysed by Osmium tetroxide⁷⁻¹⁰. The oxidation of glycerol by different oxidants such as potassium permanganate, potassium peroxydisulphate and ceric sulphate etc. has been studied in the past¹¹⁻¹³. Various oxidation products of glycerol such as formaldehyde, formic acid, glyceric acid and tartronic acid have been reported. The present paper deals with the kinetic studies of the oxidation of glycerol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) catalysed by Osmium tetroxide.

Experimental

Aqueous potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) was prepared from Analar BDH sample and the concentration was checked by iodometry¹⁴. 1 g capsule of Osmium tetroxide was dissolved in a litre measuring flask in 16 ml of N.A.R. sulphuric acid and diluted upto mark with double distilled water to get $\frac{M}{254}$

Osmium tetroxide solution. All other chemicals used were also A.R. or extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. The reaction vessels were coated with black varnish to exclude photochemical effect.

The requisite amounts of glycerol, sodium hydroxide and Osmium tetroxide solutions were taken in the reaction flask and kept in a thermostat at the desired temperature within the range of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The flask containing hexacyanoferrate (III) solution was also kept in the thermostat. The reaction was started by adding requisite volume of hexacyanoferrate (III) solution. The kinetics of the reaction was followed by estimating the unconsumed hexacyanoferrate (III) iodometrically. Owing to high initial concentration of the alkali ($[\text{OH}^-] = 0.4M$) the pH remained constant during the progress of the reaction.

Results

The reaction was studied at different temperatures and concentrations of the substrate, oxidant, sodium hydroxide and the catalyst. It was observed that under all the conditions disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III) followed a zero order kinetics. The exact nature of the reaction is shown in Figure 1

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of each constituent.

- [1] $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{Glycerol}] = 1.33 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4 \times 10^{-1}M$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 3.93 \times 10^{-5}M$, Temp. = 45° .
- [2] $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = [\text{Glycerol}] = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4 \times 10^{-1}M$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 7.83 \times 10^{-5}M$, Temp. = 45° .
- [3] $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = [\text{Glycerol}] = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 3 \times 10^{-1}M$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 3.93 \times 10^{-5}M$, Temp. = 45° .
- [4] $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = [\text{Glycerol}] = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4 \times 10^{-1}M$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 3.93 \times 10^{-5}M$, Temp. = 45° .
- [5] $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = [\text{Glycerol}] = 5 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{NaOH}] = 4 \times 10^{-1}M$, $[\text{OsO}_4] = 3.93 \times 10^{-5}M$, Temp. = 60° .

The lines in the figure are numbered [1] to [5] from bottom to top.

in which the typical zero plots for the oxidation of glycerol under different conditions have been given.

Stoichiometry

To determine the number of moles of hexacyanoferrate (III) consumed per mole of glycerol, a known amount of glycerol was mixed with 15 to 20 times its molar concentration of alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) along with OsO_4 as catalyst and the mixture was kept for several days in an oven at 30° till the reaction was complete. The results of two different sets are recorded in Table 1(a).

TABLE 1(a)

Set I			Set II		
[Fe(CN) $_6$] $^{3-}$ = $50 \times 10^{-3} M$			[Fe(CN) $_6$] $^{3-}$ = $50 \times 10^{-3} M$		
[Glycerol] = $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$			[Glycerol] = $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$		
[NaOH] = $0.4 M$			[NaOH] = $0.4 M$		
[OsO $_4$] = $3.93 \times 10^{-5} M$			[OsO $_4$] = $3.93 \times 10^{-5} M$		
Time (days)	Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$ reacted (moles l $^{-1}$) $\times 10^3$	Moles of Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$ reacted per mole of glycerol	Time (days)	Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$ reacted (moles l $^{-1}$) $\times 10^3$	Moles of Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$ reacted per mole of glycerol
10	39.75		10	29.5	
15	40.00	12.01	15	30.0	12.0
20	40.00		20	30.0	

The above data indicate that 12 moles of Fe(CN)_6^{3-} are consumed for one mole of glycerol. The stoichiometry may, thus, be represented by the equation

Formic acid was detected in the distillate of the reaction mixture by the chromotropic acid reaction¹⁵. For quantitative estimation of formic acid 100 ml of the reaction mixture containing 0.01 mole each of glycerol and Fe(CN)_6^{3-} at $[\text{OH}^-] = 2M$ along with OsO_4 as catalyst were kept in a thermostat at 45° till the reaction was complete. The mixture was then neutralised and subjected to distillation in presence of small excess of sulphuric acid in order to decompose sodium formate present in the mixture. The results are recorded in Table 1(b).

TABLE 1(b)

Moles of Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$ reacted	Moles of glycerol reacted*	Moles of formic acid formed
1×10^{-7}	8.3×10^{-4}	7.4×10^{-4}

* From stoichiometry.

The above results are fairly in agreement with the proposed stoichiometry.

Kinetics

Dependence on the oxidant concentration

The reaction was studied at different concentrations of hexacyanoferrate (III) keeping other parameters constant and the results are given in Table 2. It is seen from the Table 2 that the zero order rate constants are fairly constant over a ten fold variation in the concentration. However, at higher concentrations they are somewhat greater than that at lower concentrations. This increase in the zero order rate constant values might be taken as due to secondary salt effect and it is valid to assume the zero order

dependence of the reaction rate on hexacyanoferrate (III) ion concentration.

TABLE 2.

[Glycerol] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$; [NaOH] = $4 \times 10^{-1} M$; [Fe(CN) $_6$] $^{3-} \times 10^3$ mole l $^{-1}$	[OsO $_4$] = $3.93 \times 10^{-5} M$; Temp. = 45° .	2.0	2.5	3.33	5.0	10.0	20.0
$k_0 \times 10^5$ mole l $^{-1}$ min $^{-1}$		2.80	2.76	3.20	3.20	3.30	3.04

Dependence on glycerol concentration

The k_0 values are directly proportional to the concentration of glycerol (Fig. 2) indicating the first

Fig. 2. Effect of variation of glycerol concentration, Temp. 45°
[Fe(CN) $_6$ $^{3-}$] = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaOH] = $4 \times 10^{-1} M$,
[OsO $_4$] = $3.93 \times 10^{-5} M$.

order dependence of the reaction with respect to the substrate.

Dependence on Sodium hydroxide concentration

The reaction was studied at different concentrations of NaOH keeping a constant ionic strength of unity, by adding corresponding amounts of NaClO₄, the contribution of Fe(CN)₆³⁻ ions being neglected. The results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3

[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = [Glycerol] = 5 × 10⁻³M,
[OsO₄] = 3.93 × 10⁻⁵M,
Ionic strength = 1M Temp. = 45°C.

[NaOH] × 10 Mole l ⁻¹	[NaClO ₄] × 10 Mole l ⁻¹	k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	$\frac{k_0}{[\text{NaOH}]} \times 10^4$
2.0	8.0	2.00	1.00
3.0	7.0	3.13	1.04
4.0	6.0	4.13	1.03
5.0	5.0	5.00	1.00
6.0	4.0	5.88	0.98

The results show that the rate of reaction has a first order dependence on NaOH concentration.

Dependence on Osmium tetroxide

The Figure 3 shows that the zero order rate constant increases proportionally with an increase in the

Fig. 3. Effect of variation of Osmium tetroxide concentration, Temp. 45°C.
[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = [Glycerol] = 5 × 10⁻³M,
[NaOH] = 6 × 10⁻¹M.

concentration of catalyst showing that the reaction has first order dependence in the catalyst concentration.

Salt effect

The reaction was studied in presence of potassium chloride and potassium sulphate. The results are shown in the Table 4.

It is seen from the table that potassium chloride and potassium sulphate have a slight catalytic effect.

TABLE 4

[Glycerol] = [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 5 × 10⁻³M, [NaOH] = 4 × 10⁻¹M
[OsO₄] = 3.93 × 10⁻⁵M, Temp. = 45°C.

Salt	Concentration mole l ⁻¹ × 10	k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
—	—	2.72
KCl	1.0	3.40
	2.0	3.77
K ₂ SO ₄	1.0	3.32
	2.0	4.02

Temperature dependence

Reaction was studied at different temperatures and thermodynamic parameters have been calculated.

TABLE 5

[Glycerol] = [Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 5 × 10⁻³M, [NaOH] = 4 × 10⁻¹M
[OsO₄] = 3.93 × 10⁻⁵M.

Temperature °C	40	45	50	55	60
k ₀ × 10 ⁵ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	1.9	2.7	3.6	4.8	6.2

The temperature coefficient, energy and entropy of activation have been calculated to be 1.83, 12.23 Kcals/mole and -25.1 e.u. respectively.

Discussions

On the basis of our experimental data, the rate of reaction may be given by the equation

$$\frac{-d}{dt}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = k [\text{Glycerol}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{OsO}_4]$$

We propose the following mechanism :

The above mechanism is in agreement with that proposed by Mehrotra and Mushran⁷ for the Osmium tetroxide catalysed oxidation of some organic compounds by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III).

From the above scheme, it is seen that the intermediate anion of the glycerol formed in step (1) forms an unstable complex with Osmium tetroxide which rapidly decomposes giving the products and the reduced Osmium species which is then oxidised to osmium tetroxide by the fast reaction (4). The reaction (2) is the slowest and controls the rate of the reaction. Applying the steady state treatment to the various intermediate, the following rate law equation may be derived.

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} \text{H}_2\text{O}} [\text{CH}_2\text{OH} \cdot \text{CHOH} \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{OH}] \times [\text{OH}^-][\text{OsO}_4] \quad \dots (5)$$

The above rate expression is in agreement with the experimental data.

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